

HYPERCHOLESTEROLEMIA AS A RISK FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES

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ABSTRACT

Hypercholesterolemia is a pathological condition that develops due to elevated total cholesterol levels in the blood plasma (the threshold is 5 mmol per liter). The disease is caused by endocrine disorders, genetic defects, and failure to maintain a balanced diet. The condition often occurs without clinical manifestations; in rare cases, xanthomas (nodular lesions) may form on the skin. Untreated hypercholesterolemia can lead to the development of atherosclerosis.

Introduction. Hypercholesterolemia is a key risk factor for the development of atherosclerotic vascular changes and cardiac complications.

In Russia, the prevalence of elevated cholesterol among adults exceeds 35%, in Uzbekistan it is approximately 30–34%, and in European countries it reaches 40% or more. Despite the introduction of screening programs, many patients remain undiagnosed or inadequately monitored, reinforcing the need for improved cardiovascular risk assessment methods.

It is crucial to differentiate between primary and secondary dyslipidemias, as treatment strategies will differ fundamentally.

Primary dyslipidemias are genetic in nature and develop as a result of abnormalities in genes involved in lipid metabolism. In these cases, they manifest as familial (inherited) lipid metabolism disorders. FH is an inherited autosomal dominant disorder caused by gene mutations, characterized by persistently elevated levels of "bad cholesterol" (LDL-C) and the early development of atherosclerosis and premature coronary heart disease (CHD).

The main causes of secondary dyslipidemias are diabetes mellitus (DM), hypothyroidism, and chronic kidney disease (CKD).

A distinction is made between modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors that lead to the development of CVD.

Non-modifiable risk factors include age, gender, and a family history of CVD. Modifiable factors include dyslipidemia (DLP), arterial hypertension (AH), smoking, type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and an unhealthy lifestyle (obesity, physical inactivity, a diet with excessive consumption of saturated fats and refined carbohydrates).

Purpose of the study. To assess cardiovascular risk in patients with hypercholesterolemia.

Material and research methods. A prospective observational cohort study was conducted at the Fergana Cardiology Center for the period 2022-2025. The study population was divided into two study groups: the main group - 450 patients with hypercholesterolemia (LDL-C ≥ 3.0 mmol/L); the control group - 300 patients with normal lipid parameters..

Research methods:

- collection of medical history and clinical and demographic data;
- measurement of total cholesterol, LDL, HDL, and triglyceride levels;
- blood pressure assessment;
- assessment of associated risk factors (smoking, obesity, diabetes);
- use of risk assessment scales (e.g., SCORE, Framingham).

The statistical analysis included the following: descriptive statistics (mean values, %); χ^2 test for categorical variables; logistic regression for risk predictor analysis significance level $p < 0.05$.

Results and discussion. When assessing cardiovascular risk using the SCORE scale, high and very high risk of cardiovascular events ($\geq 5\%$) was observed in 41.5% of the study group and 18.7% of the control group ($p < 0.001$). Patients with a combination of hypercholesterolemia and arterial hypertension had a more than 3-fold increased risk of developing coronary heart disease (CHD) compared with patients without these factors (OR = 3.4; 95% CI 2.1–5.2).

Among patients with hypercholesterolemia:

- 41.1% have concomitant arterial hypertension;
- 28.9% smoke tobacco;
- 19.8% have diabetes.

This is consistent with international observational data, where a combination of risk factors significantly increases the likelihood of cardiovascular events.

These findings indicate that hypercholesterolemia is associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular disease, especially in the presence of comorbid risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, and smoking. These results are consistent with European and Russian studies, where high LDL levels are considered one of the leading predictors of coronary heart disease and myocardial infarction.

Conclusions:

1. Patients with hypercholesterolemia have a significantly higher cardiovascular risk compared to individuals with normal lipid levels.
2. The combination of hypercholesterolemia with other risk factors (hypertension, diabetes, smoking) significantly increases the likelihood of developing coronary heart disease and other cardiovascular events.
3. Comprehensive risk assessment and early intervention are necessary to reduce cardiovascular complications in this group of patients..

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